

THE FATIGUE OF CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITES CONTAINING INTERLAMINAR INKJET PRINTED POLYMER DROPLETS

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ABSTRACT

An inkjet printing process was used to deposit droplets of poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) in a regular hexagonal array onto the surface of a unidirectional carbon fibre prepreg material in order to create a toughened interlaminar layer. In previous work, Zhang et al. [1, 2] showed that this process can be used to improve the interlaminar fracture toughness of carbon fibre prepreps by up to 50%.

4 point bending tests were carried out in both static and cyclic loading to determine how this toughened layer influenced the properties of the composite laminate in flexural loading. As part of this work, several suggestions are made for the optimisation of 4 point bending tests. These modifications were shown to increase the measured flexural strength of the laminates by 57% when compared to a basic 4 point bending setup. Static 4 point bending tests were carried out in accordance with BS EN ISO 14125:1998+A1:2011 on both unprinted “virgin” laminates and laminates printed with an ink of 10%/wt Poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) in dimethylformamide (DMF). Results showed little or no change in the static properties of the composite, with the flexural moduli of the virgin and printed composites being 106.3GPa and 104.3GPa respectively. The flexural strength of the virgin and printed composites were found to be 2.23GPa and 2.29GPa respectively. Fatigue tests were also carried out in 4 point bending. The results showed little change in the fatigue life of the material, although a slight decrease as well as increased in data scatter may have been observed in the printed material.

1. INTRODUCTION

The use and popularity of fibre reinforced polymer (FRP) composites has increased in recent decades. This is owing to their excellent tensile strength and stiffness. Of these materials, carbon fibre reinforced composites offer the highest specific stiffness and strength. Industries such as aerospace, which demand extreme weight savings without compromising performance, have long been a major driving force behind composites research. Both airbus and Boeing now manufacture civil aircraft that have fuselages comprising over 50% composite materials: the A350 XWB and 787 Dreamliner respectively.

Fatigue may be defined as the decrease of the material's load-bearing capacity under cyclic loading, resulting in failure at stress levels below its normal engineering strength. It was common at one time for designers of composite structures to consider composites, specifically carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) composites, as immune to fatigue [3]. However, it is now firmly established that composite materials, like metals, may suffer from degradation of material properties under cyclic loading which can be described as fatigue. In safety critical industries such as aerospace then, it is gravely important to understand how fatigue damage develops in in-service components so that timely repairs and replacements can be made before catastrophic failure occurs.

Fatigue in metals is a well-established area of research, and has been studied for more than a century. Fatigue in metals often progresses by the initiation of a single crack, which then extends through the component until failure occurs. The bulk material away from the crack is generally unchanged throughout the process, although the material may harden somewhat. The mechanisms of composite fatigue, however, are vastly different to those in metals. “Composites accumulate damage in a general rather than a localized fashion, and failure does not always occur by the propagation of a

single macroscopic crack. The micro-structural mechanisms of damage accumulation, including fibre breakage and matrix cracking, debonding, transverse-ply cracking, and delamination, occur sometimes independently and sometimes interactively, and the predominance of one or the other may be strongly affected by both materials variables and testing conditions” [3].

Delamination growing under fatigue is potentially the more critical mode of damage. Although it may not cause total failure of the load bearing capabilities of the composite, it is usually a precursor to it, severely impairing mechanical performance [4, 5]. Therefore, if delaminations (or the mechanisms which cause delaminations) can be slowed or arrested then the structure may maintain some integrity, and the working life of the component will be extended.

In this work, a solution containing a thermoplastic polymer is deposited in a regular hexagonal array of droplets by inkjet printing onto the surface of a unidirectional carbon fibre prepreg. A series of these prepreg layers are then laid up in the usual manner to form a composite laminate, and are cured in an autoclave, creating a composite laminate which contains interlaminar polymer droplet layers. It is hypothesised that these droplets may inhibit fatigue crack and/or delamination growth by increasing the energy required to fracture the material through one of two methods: either by increasing the crack path length where the crack circumvents the droplet, or by plastic deformation of the polymer should the crack go directly through the droplet.

Inkjet printing is a non-contact, highly scalable technique, which can be used to deposit picolitre scale droplets onto the surface of a substrate in a precise manner [6, 7]. This capability allows precise control over the droplet distribution, allowing them to be deposited exclusively where they might be required, greatly reducing the weight of polymer that must be added to gain the benefits of doing so.

2. BACKGROUND

This work is based on work conducted by Zhang et al [1, 2]. In this work they investigated several different polymer and solvent combinations, with poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG) in deionised water, and poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) in dimethylformamide (DMF) producing the most favourable results. The “inks” were printed onto a carbon fibre prepreg substrate in a regular hexagonal array, which was then laid up in the usual manner to form a composite laminate that contains interlaminar polymer droplets.

Figure 1. Printed hexagonal pattern on carbon fibre prepreg

Double cantilever beam (DCB) tests were conducted in order to establish the interlaminar fracture toughness (G_{IC}). It was found that the interlaminar fracture toughness of the composite materials were increased by up to 50%. The increase is of a similar magnitude to that observed in previous work by Yasaei et al. where thermoplastic toughening materials were applied [8]. The most significant increase

in G_{IC} was found using a 10% PMMA in DMF ink printed onto Cycom 977-2-35-12KHTS-268-300 prepreg. This work therefore used this ink and prepreg as a starting point.

Other authors have investigated interlaminar toughening using polymer materials. One of the most common methods for improving the interlaminar fracture toughness is interleaving, in which a distinct interlayer (thermoset or thermoplastic) is added between the laminate plies. This provides an area which absorbs energy and inhibits cracks which may otherwise propagate between plies.

Askoy and Carlsson [9] experimented with both thermoset and thermoplastic interleaves to determine what effect the thickness of the interleaf had on the mechanical properties. They found that thicker interleaves increased fracture toughness and shear yielding of the material around the crack tip up to a point at which the effects levelled off. Predictably, they found that thermoset interleaves proved less effective than thermoplastic ones. Thermoplastics allow much greater plastic deformation with less microcracking and therefore crack tip shielding.

Lu et al. [10] inserted thin (~0.1mm) sheets of poly(ethylene-co-acrylic acid) (PEAA) between plies of carbon fibre prepreg. Interestingly, they noted a significant change in the failure mechanism of the composite in both impact and static bending. The presence of the interleaved layer provided a barrier to prevent the compressive cracks from propagating into the tensile plies of the samples. This also had the effect of slightly decreasing the flexural modulus of the composite, which they attributed to the interleaved layer allowing the adjacent plies to move separately more easily.

Hojo et al. [11] used the epoxy matrix as the interleaf material by sequentially laying up half-cured epoxy films and prepregs. It was reported that the G_{IC} values of the laminates with the self-same epoxy interleaves were almost identical to those of the base laminates. However, the initial values and the PROP values of G_{IIc} in the laminates with interleaves were 160% and 340% higher than those of the base CFRPs, respectively.

Hamer et al. [12] demonstrated approximately 300% improvement in G_{IC} values compared to the base laminates using an electro-spun Nylon-6,6 nanofibrous mat as the interlaminar toughener.

Takeda et al. [13, 14] used fine, randomly dispersed polyamide particles to create a toughened interlaminar layer between prepreg plies. They found that delamination onset and growth are suppressed by the toughened interlaminar layers; although they don't directly quantify this improvement. Using a modified Paris' Law they characterised the transverse crack multiplication and delamination growth.

3. 4 POINT BENDING AS A VIABLE TEST PROCEDURE

Since the polymer reinforcement is situated in the interlaminar region, it is likely that the greatest influence will be towards delaminations. With this in mind, a test procedure was developed which encouraged delaminations to occur. Where increased interlaminar shear stresses are required, many authors choose to opt for a multidirectional stacking sequence in tensile fatigue loading due to the simplicity of the tests and the relevance of multidirectional laminates in real-world applications. However, flexural fatigue offers other benefits that tensile fatigue cannot. Firstly, we may introduce interlaminar shear stresses without adding complexity. Whilst multidirectional composites better represent real composite stacking sequences, the strain interactions between the differently orientated plies complicate the loading scenario. Flexural fatigue offers the opportunity to test unidirectional composites; which allows us to understand the interlaminar damage mechanics at a much more fundamental level. Flexural fatigue then, is well suited to those who wish to investigate the fundamental damage mechanics of composites in the interlaminar region.

Flexural fatigue also offers other advantages. In scenarios where laminates will be subject to a high degree of bending, flexural fatigue is an obvious choice. It also offers greatly reduced loading requirements; a huge benefit to institutions with limited large capacity testing facilities. It also brings increased measurability. In order to measure the strain, of specimens in tensile fatigue it is necessary to use such instrumentation as strain gauges or clip-on gauges, which may come unstuck or move during tests. Clip-on gauges must also be removed before failure or else damage to the gauge is risked. Strain in flexural fatigue is measured using the midpoint deflection of the specimen (vertical deflection of the sample at the central point of the span, i.e. the maximum deflection from the starting position).

In 3 point bending this is simply the loading roller displacement. In 4 point bending it is necessary to measure the midpoint displacement using other instrumentation. Whichever setup is chosen, the benefit of this measurement is that deflections are much more pronounced since bending produces large deflections; and as a result, any changes in deflection due to reductions in stiffness are much more measurable than in tensile setups, requiring less complex and accurate measurement.

Flexural fatigue then, has many advantages, but these are often disregarded in favour of the less complex and more easily modelled tensile tests. As a result, applicable literature which utilises flexural fatigue does exist [15-24], but is somewhat uncommon.

All static and fatigue tests in this paper used a custom 4 point bend jig setup as shown in Figure 2a which adhered to BS EN ISO 14125:1998+A1:2011. This setup used 5mm rollers which sat in machined channels to allow limited rotation. However, poor test repeatability and lower than expected flexural strengths were deemed a significant issue that needed to be overcome in order to achieve accurate data. Several modifications were made to the design to ensure procedural repeatability. Specimen retaining jaws were installed in order to keep the specimen captive, preventing out of plane movement (Figure 2b). Legs were fixed to one half of the jig to ensure jig alignment relative to the sample at all times (Figure 2c). Roller bearings and larger (10mm) diameter rollers were installed to replace the central rollers (Figure 2c) to reduce stress concentrations at the loading points. The roller mounts had a degree of adjustability built in to enable the user to level the rollers against the specimen surface, providing equal load distribution between the rollers. Finally, a fixed LVDT bracket was added to guarantee that the measured midpoint deflection was relative to the test jig, and not to another surface. It also helped to prevent the LVDT from incurring damage upon the failure of the sample.

Although both the standard and modified jigs adhered to the testing standard, static test results showed that these modifications increased the measured flexural strength of the CFRP specimens by 57%. It may be reasoned then, that the importance of proper test setup, and the subjectivity of test results described in literary references should never be overlooked.

Figure 2: a) Basic, adjustable 4 point bending fixture, b) Developed 4 point bending fixture, front view showing roller bearings, c) Developed 4 point bending fixture, d) Rear view showing LVDT midpoint displacement sensor and bracket.

4. TESTING

4.1. STATIC TESTS

Several static 4 point bend tests were conducted on 977-2 CFRP in order to establish the flexural strength and modulus of the material in both its virgin and printed (10%/wt PMMA) varieties. These tests were used to determine the flexural properties of the composite laminates, and also to provide a basis for the subsequent flexural fatigue tests.

5 virgin and 5 printed (10%/wt PMMA in DMF) 15x2x100mm unidirectional (0°) specimens consisting of 8 unidirectional plies of Cycom 977-2-35-12KHTS-268-300 prepreg were put under 4 point flexural loading using a 4 point bending jig in accordance with BS EN ISO 14125:1998+A1:2011. A support span of 81mm and a top roller separation of 27mm were used. Specimens were placed under compressive flexural force at a rate of 2mm/min until ultimate failure. Force, crosshead displacement, and midpoint deflection were recorded.

2 layers of Polyvinyl Chloride (PVC) electrical insulation tape were placed at the load application points to enable load distribution. This was done as an alternative to the ISO standard suggestion of using a 0.2mm polypropylene (PP) shim. It was decided that PVC had similar properties to PP, and had the added advantage of being adhesive. Additionally, the tape used was 0.1mm in thickness; thus, 2 layers provided a shim thickness in line with the testing standard. Test results showed that the measured flexural strength of samples which used a tape shim were on average 37% higher than those which used no shim.

An RDP D5 series LVDT was used with a custom lever arm attachment in order to obtain the midpoint deflection.

The average flexural moduli and ultimate flexural strength of the virgin and printed samples were calculated using equations 1 and 2.

$$E_f = \frac{0.21L^3}{bh^3} \left(\frac{\Delta F}{\Delta s} \right) \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma_f = \frac{FL}{bh^2} \quad (2)$$

where;

E_f is the flexural modulus of elasticity (Pa)

σ_f is the flexural stress (Pa)

L is the span length of the specimen (m)

F is the load (N)

b is the average specimen width along the central third of the specimen(m)

h is the specimen thickness along the central third of the specimen (m)

ΔF is the change in load over the measured portion of the load/displacement data (N)

Δs is the change in deflection over the measured portion of the load/displacement data (m)

Property	Printing	Units	Value	Standard Deviation
E_f	None	GPa	106.3	2.4
E_f	10%/wt PMMA in DMF	GPa	104.3	4.7
σ_f	None	MPa	2230	35.8
σ_f	10%/wt PMMA in DMF	MPa	2290	99.5

Table 1: Average results of static tests performed on both virgin and printed composite samples.

4.2. FATIGUE TESTS

Fatigue tests in a 4 point bending setup were conducted on both the virgin and printed unidirectional composite laminates. The setup of the fatigue tests was the same as the static tests described in section 4.1. Both virgin and printed (10%/wt PMMA in DMF) 15x2x100mm unidirectional (0°) specimens consisting of 8 unidirectional plies of Cycom 977-2-35-12KHTS-268-300 prepreg were put under 4 point flexural loading using a 4 point bending jig in accordance with BS EN ISO 13003:2003. A support span of 81mm and a top roller separation of 27mm were used. 2 layers of PVC electrical insulation tape were placed at the load application points to enable load distribution. A Nene 12.5kN servo-hydraulic testing machine controlled by a MOOG SmartTEST ONE test controller was used to perform the tests.

All tests were load (stress) controlled. The samples were cycled at 5Hz at a load ratio of $R=0.1$ in all tests. Failure was defined by the complete fracture of the samples. The maximum loading force for each specimen was calculated from equation 2, where σ_f was taken to be 2.23GPa for virgin samples, and 2.29GPa for printed samples. A minimum of 3 samples were tested at each chosen stress level. Any sample which reached 1×10^6 cycles was deemed to have ‘run out’, and was stopped and recorded as ‘no failure’.

Test data was recorded periodically using an external National Instruments NI USB-6008 data acquisition unit. This was connected via USB to a computer, which acted as a data recorder. An NI LabView script was developed to control the unit. The values obtained from the tests were: time, force, position (actuator), and midpoint deflection. The sample period of these tests varied to suit the test so as to avoid excessive amounts of data. A complete waveform consisting of 20 data points was captured at each sample interval to ensure that the maximum and minimum values of each data series were recorded.

Using the recorded force and displacement data, the flexural stiffness of the samples was calculated from equation 1 at regular intervals throughout the tests. This data was used to provide insight into the damage mechanisms driving the failure at the various stress amplitudes used in the tests.

Figure 3: Fatigue life diagram of unidirectional 977-2 CFRP

5. DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the results of the static 4 point bend tests. Although limited, there are two main conclusions that may be drawn from the results of the static tests. Firstly, there appears to be little or no change in the physical properties of the printed material in static testing. A 3% increase in static strength may be seen, although the errors of these tests overlap, so this may not be said with any certainty. An increase in strength is possible however, since the PMMA droplets may enable some minor plastic deformation in the interlaminar region, reducing interlaminar stresses. They might also impede or arrest delaminations, further stabilizing the stiffness of the material. Secondly, it is notable that the standard deviation of results obtained from the printed composites is larger than those of their virgin equivalents. This may be explained by the reduced homogeneity of the matrix material in the interlaminar region, resulting in a more random progression of cracks.

Figure 3 shows the S-N curve produced from the 4 point bending fatigue tests. These results compare favourably with curves suggested by Lomov et al. [25] (Figure 4) and Harris [3] amongst others. Only a limited amount of scatter is observable in the data, indicating good experimental consistency. In other fatigue tests, a more basic version of the 4 point bending jig was used, but a large degree of scatter was present, prompting some of the upgrades referred to in section 3.

Figure 4: Typical composite S-N curve produced by Lomov et al. [25] showing distinct low (II) and high (III) cycle fatigue regions

Firstly, it is observed that the printed composite appears to produce more scattered results than the virgin composite; an observation which holds consistent with what was observed in static tests.

The results appear to show a slight decrease in fatigue life of the printed composite compared to the virgin composite; particularly in the high-cycle fatigue region, although it is not possible to say this for certain due to the scatter of the results. However, this observation may be supported when we consider that as the number of cycles to failure are increased, the dominant mechanism of failure shifts from fibre-dominated mechanisms to matrix-dominated [26, 27]. As the printing method only affects the interlaminar region, it would be reasonable to assume that high-cycle fatigue would be affected much more than low-cycle fatigue. It is difficult to say at this stage why exactly printed composites would suffer from reduced fatigue lives. The most likely hypotheses at this point are that the polymer droplets either interact chemically with the resin system, or that they create stress concentration points within the material, assisting crack propagation. The author leans towards the latter theory.

The flexural stiffness of the specimens was recorded throughout the tests, providing data which can be used to analyse the damage mechanisms which lead to failure. Generally, it may be noted that the recorded stiffness in these tests was considerably higher (up to 40%) than in static testing. This is

attributed to the testing frequency. Higher strain rates inevitably result in higher apparent stiffness. This artefact of cyclic testing should be considered when comparing static and fatigue tests, but it is not detrimental to the results. In fact, higher test frequencies are generally more representative of the cyclic loads encountered by in-service components. It is beyond the extent of this paper to analyse the data in full. Instead, a brief discussion of each stress level will be given using a representative specimen from both virgin and printed samples at each stress level.

5.1. Tests carried out at $\sigma = 0.85, 0.8, \& 0.7$

At these stresses we see fibre-dominated failure, and as a result, very little stiffness change is observed. We also see little or no variation between the virgin and printed composites since any influence to the material properties would most likely only be noticeable in matrix-dominated failure due to the way in which the printing process is applied. Also, aside from the obvious decrease in life with increased stress, the shape of the curves is quite similar in most cases. Generally, specimens see a brief increase in stiffness, which can be attributed to fibres aligning in the direction of the load in the initial cycles, and to increased fibre strain as weaker fibres fracture, which has been shown by Genedy et al. and Johnston and Gates [28, 29] to increase stiffness. After this, variations between the stress levels start to occur. At $\sigma=0.85$ (Figure 5) and $\sigma=0.8$ (Figure 6), after the initial increase in stiffness, the stiffness generally remains constant to failure. In this case, the fibres have completed their alignment, but no significant matrix damage has occurred yet.

At $\sigma=0.7$ (Figure 7), it can be seen that the stiffness remains constant, but in some cases begins to decrease steadily until failure. In this case, matrix damage is beginning to increase, and affects the stiffness of the laminate to a greater degree than any continued fibre alignment or increased fibre strain [3].

Figure 5: Stiffness degradation comparison of virgin and printed (10%/wt PMMA in DMF) unidirectional (977-2 resin system) 4 point bend fatigue samples at a stress amplitude of 0.85

Figure 6: Stiffness degradation comparison of virgin and printed (10%/wt PMMA in DMF) unidirectional (977-2 resin system) 4 point bend fatigue samples at a stress amplitude of 0.8

Figure 7: Stiffness degradation comparison of virgin and printed (10%/wt PMMA in DMF) unidirectional (977-2 resin system) 4 point bend fatigue samples at a stress amplitude of 0.7

5.2. Tests carried out at $\sigma = 0.65$ & 0.6

It is at these stress levels that the specimens enter into the high-cycle region, and matrix-dominated failure becomes prominent.

At $\sigma=0.65$ (Figure 8) a large variation in fatigue lives are observed. Matrix damage occurs over a much greater range of cycles. It is notable at this stress level that in those specimens which exceeded 100 thousand cycles, a gradual drop in stiffness is followed by a significant, clearly visible drop-off in stiffness; a definite indicator of impending failure which has been noted by various authors [3, 30, 31].

Finally, at $\sigma=0.6$ (Figure 9) the composite enters into the very-high-cycle region, with most specimens exceeding 100 thousand cycles. Here we notice significant falls in stiffness, causing a 'plateau' effect. This may be significant damage events, such as delaminations, occurring and becoming arrested; although current experimental data cannot prove this.

As a whole, this data provides an excellent insight into the damage mechanisms at work in these experiments. And given better understanding, may also provide a way of tracking and predicting damage and failure.

Figure 8: Stiffness degradation comparison of virgin and printed (10%/wt PMMA in DMF) unidirectional (977-2 resin system) 4 point bend fatigue samples at a stress amplitude of 0.65

Figure 9: Stiffness degradation comparison of virgin and printed (10%/wt PMMA in DMF) unidirectional (977-2 resin system) 4 point bend fatigue samples at a stress amplitude of 0.6

6. CONCLUSIONS

This work has explored a new method of interlaminar toughening as a possible method of increasing the fatigue life of carbon fibre composites. Although initial results have shown there to be little or no change in fatigue life thus far, this work will be used to understand and optimise the effect of the printing pattern on the fatigue life of the composites in future work. Alternative polymers, droplet sizes, and printing patterns will be explored with the aim of finding the optimal printing method which benefits both interlaminar fracture toughness and fatigue life.

4 point bending was explored as a possible method of inducing delaminations. The benefits of this method over tensile fatigue were debated, and were considered advantageous, particularly where fundamental understanding of fatigue damage is required, and where large-scale testing machines are unavailable. As part of this work, several suggestions are made for the optimisation of 4 point bending tests. These suggestions were shown to increase the measured flexural strength of the laminates by 57% when compared to a basic 4 point bending setup.

Results showed little or no change in the static properties of the composite, with the flexural moduli of the virgin and printed composites being 106.3GPa and 104.3GPa respectively. The flexural strength of the virgin and printed composites were found to be 2.23GPa and 2.29GPa respectively.

Likewise, in cyclic loading the printed composites showed very little change in fatigue life over the virgin composite, although a slight decrease in fatigue life may have been observed. It is unclear yet whether this is due to the low concentration of polymer introduced, or whether it is due to the chosen test method.

Despite these results, the author is optimistic that this method may yet be beneficial to the fatigue life of the composite given the positive results found by Zhang et al. Alternative toughening polymers are likely to produce differing effects, and these will be explored in future work.

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